

A Review on Hybrid Fuel Powered Tilt Wing Drones

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Abstract— Tilt wing drones are a unique type of machine which incorporates the functionality of helicopters and fixed wing flight. It utilizes the VTOL capabilities of the copter and cruise speed of the fixed wing flight to achieve greater performance and result. As it is the world perspective, nowadays drones are a significant technological availability in numerous sectors it has been involved heavily in Military, logistics, surveillance, Agriculture even in domestic sector it has been begun to involve acutely. The drones are used as a delivery agent, rescue services are often opting drone services as it has tremendous advantage that it can reach and provide services much faster in many cases being lifesaving. As the importance of Drones has become a certainty we review in this paper about the applications and development of hybrid fuel powered tiltwing drone using IC engine and electric motor, its principle, advantages, challenges and finally the future developments of this machine.

1. Introduction

The rise in development and research of unmanned UAV have been on the rise for the last two decades, they are compacted and developed for multipurpose activity to contest multitude of objectives that are expensive to achieve or too dangerous to approach by humans [1]. With the requirement of UAV being diversified they have been expanding the types of UAV based on their flight modes, applications, missions and can be categorized into three: Fixed wing UAVs (FW), Rotor wing UAVs (multi-rotor) and hybrid UAVs [2].

Hybrid UAVs are which include both capabilities of fixed wing UAV and Rotor wing UAVs, in this paper the principles, advantages, challenges and future developments of a hybrid fuel powered tilt wing drone using an IC engine and Electric motors is discussed. In order to understand the necessity for this type of UAV it is required to know why it is necessary to combine the functions of two different type of UAVs. In case of fixed wing drones they have long range and speed, but requires a runway for take-off and landing on the other hand rotor type drones have hovering capability and manoeuvrability but they have high mechanical difficulty, low speed and range [1]. In order to overcome such limitation a hybrid UAV is apposite.

1.1 Tilt wing drone

The tilt wing drone is enabled with features of both FW and rotor type UAVs, the drone is fitted-out with long range, long flight, large payload capacity with VTOL take-off and landing capabilities to carry out mission for which require rapid response and environmental and geographical limitation [3]. A look into the overview of the FW, rotor UAV, and hybrid approach can be seen in Fig 1 [4].

Fig 1 The image shows the advantages and disadvantages of fixed wing aircraft and a helicopter, along with an example of hybrid aircraft (reproduced from [4]).

In tilt wing drone the wing itself tilts around an axis with the rotors attached to the wing, it can transition from vertical position to horizontal using actuators, the control surface like ailerons and flap can be used to yaw the drone from the down flow of air from the propellers, the fixed rotors on the wing also allow to tune the aerodynamic [4].

1.2 Drone propulsion

The core of an UAV can be said to be its propulsion system, to regulate what type of mission a UAV can perform depend on its propulsion system [5]. According to energy sources, there are three ways in which propulsion system is categorized into: fuel, pure electric, and hybrid fuel-electric [5].

Many aircrafts use fuel-based propulsion such as petroleum, aviation gasoline (AvGas) they do have higher range and payload capacity but the impact on environment such as release of pollutants and greenhouse gases and depletion of fossil fuels has led to look for improvement in hybrid fuel [5,6]. Fully pure electric system a new perspective in UAV system which allow improved aerodynamics, control as small motors can be used across the fuselage with out much loss in efficiency [7]. The development of eVTOL in urban air space is an advanced transportation combination [7]. However, the idea of fully electrical propulsion system is deficient as they do not have long endurance and range due to the current low energy density of power bases [8]. The solution to overcome is the next step of integrating both fuel and electric, they are already being suited for cars and automotives [5,8].

1.2.1 Hybrid design process

Electric propulsion to be hybridized is to combine two characteristics of power, one with long cruising range and another with high power for take-off and climb and in case of combustion being hybridized is being to reduce sound produced during flight, these are also characteristic which can be achieved during hybridization [9].

The combination of fuel and electric system can be integrated in number of ways, the parallel hybrid propulsion system where the engine and motor jointly run the propellers through “mechanical drive transposition” [5]. The purpose of this to maintain the energy balance between both the engine and motor when either is insufficient its counterpart will compensate during peak load or down load [5,6,9,10]. The other method is a series connection where the engine is connected to the electrical generator which is connected to the shaft which rotates the propeller [5,6,9,11]. There are also where you split the work in which battery propulsion works during climb and the engine switches back during cruise [6]. The next type of method is fully utilizing each system the fuel is used to extend the flight after the battery propulsion has diminished [7]. A series of combination can be derived for hybrid but mostly these are the hybrid method utilized see Fig 2 [9] for the parallel, series hybridization.

Fig 2 The image show a) series hybrid method and b) parallel hybrid method (reproduced from [9]).

This review paper explores hybrid fuel tilt wing drones, analysing their advantages challenges and future development.

2. Advantages of Hybrid fuel tilt wing drones

By combining the efficiency of a fixed wing UAV and versatility of rotary wing UAV, Hybrid tilt wing UAVs has revolutionized aerial operations. With the integration of IC engine and electric motors enables long distance flight, reduced fuel consumption, enhanced operating time and manoeuvrability, making it suitable for Military, Commercial and domestic applications.

Due to various practical applications scenario, the drone might need too be active for a lengthy assignment and need to perform skill manoeuvrability under those circumstances and environmental and geographical condition [12]. Therefore, an option where you are able to choose the best drone a tilt wing drone with VTOL capabilities will enhance endurance and operational practicality [13]. They combine the benefits of the dual power sources balancing their counterpart’s weakness. The ability to achieve long flight time in regards with fully electric and IC engine supported drones is the key advantage of hybrid systems, the design of such drones enhances conversion from VTOL to fixed wing flight involve advanced procedures

that make it possible [13]. Subsequently, many researches have made its focal point to achieve high manoeuvrability while improving endurance [12].

There is a higher power to weight ratio in drones that can be applied as hybrid. Reducing weight allows higher amount of payload to be added. In fact, the author of this paper quotes from a source that the trending green energy global trend allows the popularized the electric powered hybrid vehicles [13]. Some authors research to find out the results of decreasing the weight to increase the payload, here the author decreases the weight by 3 kg too get a payload increase by 300g [14]. IC engine can produce greater uninterrupted power output without increasing weight which allows to carry extra payload or equipment's that make it suitable for allowing such drones certain required application, by low weight meaning you can add or carry extra fuel supply to assist the drone application. To quote the author "the improvement in power storage is considered the best window of opportunity to decrease the overall weight and or improve performance" [13].

Switching between the engine and battery the hybrid UAV optimizes power usage, thereby reducing the fuel required. When the drone takes off it uses both sources for maximum output and switch to engine for cruising to decrease the reliance on the battery. During transition mode the flight control surfaces helps with the lift generation reducing 30% to 50% of the actuator power from the UAV weight [15]. The author of this research journal explains that during VTOL the weight of the drone falls on the actuators and during transition it takes a slow thrust change from vertical to horizontal when the thrusters have horizontal alignment, the drone dips in altitude slightly leading to the thrust vectoring to reduce the force on the actuators to optimize the power to fixed wing flight [16]. Recent development in power distribution system have improved energy efficiency depending on the flight condition.

System redundancy is a major advantage of hybrid system. In a practical situation when there is a failure in engine or battery it will lead to failure in mission, but in hybrid systems if there is failure in engine or battery its counterpart can take over allowing the UAV to safely return or proceed based on the situation. This built in redundancy is very important in critical situation where failure is not an option. The increase in UAV in civil application and military has raised the concern of safety and failsafe requirements, the author explains a term "Fault-tolerance control system," a failsafe system having capability to handle system failure caused by components and having them safely conduct the operation with returning, the author in this paper proposed the idea of hybrid fuel drone as the failsafe for the problem [17]. Another author the use of extra battery as a redundancy factor to perform safety manoeuvring case of adverse conditions [18].

Versatility, the hybrid drones can be made from requirements and are produced and developed accordingly while the hybrid version does not just include only IC engine and battery combination or the design being limited to certain factors having the capability to develop, design, remodel based on innovation is also an advantage factor of hybrid system. The author of this paper developed a twelve-propeller drone capable of VTOL and fixed-wing functions. The drone is powered by a combination of hydrogen-driven Polymer Electrolyte Membrane fuel cells for endurance and lithium batteries for high-power situations [19]. The author proposes a design for fixed wing drones with rotors run by electric propulsion as an alternative for fixed wing with electric propulsion [20]. This is also a versatile change in perspective for using hybrid drone development.

3. Applications of Hybrid fuel tilt wing drones

Significant attention has been there on hybrid tilt wing drone for their ability perform vertical take-off and efficient forward flight. This allows them to be used in various sectors and for various application, like military reconnaissance to commercial delivery. Most of the drone used nowadays are towards surveillance as considerable time and effort has been invested in small UAV, they are used by soldiers for defence and military related purposes [21]. In this section key applications based on hybrid tilt wing drone are discussed based on latest research.

Disaster response, real time aerial assessments, search and rescue, a central role is put upon drones, and using a Hybrid drone as explained through section 2 gives advantage over such geographically unapproachable and dangerous situation [1,22,23], thus they are highly effective in disaster response and in search and rescue. To avoid loss of life and economic damage the response for disaster is estimated to be 72 hours the actions should be conducted within this hour, therefore the reaction should be quick and precise but man-made disaster brings along lot of infrastructure damage and the challenge is to setup communications and to gather data, hybrid drones play a critical role here they are capable of accessing dangerous area and are central part for the rescue operations. Aerial delivery system often underload or overload the targeted area by several meters, thus to provide real time assessment mobile network locating and providing communications through swarming the drones, Infrastructure inspection they are vital in Disaster response and search and rescue [22,23].

In modern military to hybrid drone are used due to their long-range endurance, ability to hover, adaptability, manoeuvring. They are used in surveillance and reconnaissance. The ability to hover and cruise gives a substantial gain in standings of “operational efficiency”, mostly for purpose such as long-range border patrol, guidance, navigation, reconnaissance is also prepared for numerous targets spread around the area and require adaptability of the drone to conduct intelligence analysis and other activities [24,25]. Some UAV can carry light weapon to target a conflict zone minimizing the presence of human in conflicted and dangerous area and they are also used for logistics to deliver payload for many conditions such as relief, back etc. “The hybrid system makes it able surveillance one day more” [26]. Hybrid drones provide flexibility and adaptability, making them compatible to undergo military requirements.

Abiotic and biotic factor regulates the yield of crops, growth and quality, many farmers and researchers are depending on UAV for their sensors and camera, with this they are capable of monitoring the crops [27]. There are many factors that determine a crop failure and lead to loss, crop diseases, providing of fertilizer and pesticide, crop growth and pest infection, they are resolved using hybrid drones as there is less human intervention the cause of disease reduces larger cultivation areas can be easily sprayed with fertilizer and pesticides and UAV can monitor crop growth and prevent pest control, measures soil moisture level, improve irrigation systems and can also be used to monitor livestock activity [27].

Hybrid drones are used in climate research, forest fires and wildlife protection. They can collect pollution, climate and environmental data with dedicated sensors. They can monitor endangered species, wildlife activity and survey and protect the areas of these animals without disrupting their space. Forest fires provide an obvious threat to life and property, significant increase in fires over the decade has prompted fire agencies to tackle the situation using UAV, although in the situation they provide relief measures in future they are hoped to provide research material and method for fighting fire [28].

For protection against threat and monitor public safety in urban areas the use of drone in legal manner are used. The flexibility of drone is exploited legally to monitor via “joint trajectory

design and energy management”, a suspicious link it can adjust itself to jam and eavesdrop on the link. This is done using a hybrid drone in compacted urban areas to ensure public safety [29].

Drones are also used for delivering parcel services. Due to limited range of electric drones and less flexibility of IC drones it makes the delivery of parcel difficult, hybrid drone is a new wave in delivery system with their long range, high payload capacity they can reach the delivery point feasibly, these drones are sometimes operated by humans or in most cases self-contained [30].

Hybrid drones have a diversified application from military, agriculture, fire and rescue, etc. their capability of VTOL and fixed wing modes are invaluable for modern aerial situations and with future development they can be utilised more efficiently in many sectors.

4. Future developments

Future developments in hybrid drones will focus on improving energy efficiency, enhancing autonomous capabilities, and integrating advanced materials to reduce weight while maintaining durability. The rise of A.I. can be optimized to the future development of these drones and with further development in propulsion system like fuel cells they can further enhance endurance and performance.

5. Conclusion

Hybrid drone combining Internal combustion engine and battery has come out as a oncoming development in the progress of UAV technologies. Their ability to integrate two power source of the IC engine and the battery has allowed them come out on top both fully electric and IC engine propulsion systems giving them long-range, endurance, flexibility, payload capacity, fuel efficiency, power optimization, redundancy makes them suitable for many sectors from military to commercial.

The development and research in the propulsion system in this field has shown there is a wide range of difference between the fully electric and IC engine propulsion system with their enhanced long range and endurance. The redundancy factor makes it a safe and act as a fail-safe measure for continuous flight even in diverse conditions, this is a very important point of concern in military and rescue applications.

With the developments in fuel efficiency, the introduction of hydrogen fuel cells, alternative fuel options and high battery density will improve the propulsion system. Autonomous capabilities, power management and lightweight materials will add further improvements in the future development, the introduction of A.I. and machine learning will further simplify flight controls and real time accuracy.

In conclusion, hybrid UAVs signify a foreboding technology that links the gap between endurance and efficiency. By progressing in research, it can be expected that further breakthroughs will increase their usability across various sectors. With continuous achievements these drones will become a central part in aviation industry providing enhanced, flexible and efficient solution for the coming world.

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